

Reaction of pyridine bases with dichloro-{1-(alkyl)-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole}-platinum(II). Spectroscopic and electrochemical characterization of products

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Pt(MeaaiR')Cl₂ (1) react with pyridine bases (R-Py) in presence of AgNO₃ and the products have been characterized as [Pt(MeaaiR')(R-Py)₂](ClO₄)₂ (MeaaiR' = 1-alkyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole, R' = Me (a), Et (b), CH₂Ph (c); R-Py, R = H (Py, 2), 4-Me (4-MePy, 3), 4-NMe₂ (4-NMe₂Py, 4)). The solution spectra exhibit metal-to-ligand charge transfer transition along with intraligand transitions. The coordination of the ligand has been supported by ¹H NMR spectral data. Cyclic voltammetric studies determine the involvement of azo group of the chelated ligand, MeaaiR' in the reduction process and shows azo-azo⁻ and azo⁻/azo²⁻ couples along with irreversible reduction of the coordinated R-Py.

Recently, the complexes of type M(N,N)Cl₂ (M = Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}; N,N = α-diimines¹⁻⁴) and Ru(N,N')₂Cl₂ (with *cis*-RuCl₂ configuration^{4,5}) (N,N' = unsymmetric bidentate donor ligands) attract interest in the area of chemical therapy, catalysis, photophysics, photochemistry and supramolecular chemistry. Platinum and palladium complexes with *N*-heterocycles having *cis*-MCl₂ configuration are of important because of their anti-cancer activity². To investigate the mechanism of biochemical action of metallated drugs researchers are trying to explore the *in vitro* reaction of cisplatin analogs with pyridine bases¹. In this article we wish to describe the reaction of pyridine bases with platinum(II)-MeaaiR' (MeaaiR' = 1-(alkyl)-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole) and the products have been characterized by spectroscopic and electrochemical studies. Out of different arylazoimidazoles MeaaiMe has been selected because of its advantage in characterizing the molecules with the help of ¹H NMR spectral studies.

Experimental

H₂PtCl₆.xH₂O was purchased from Arora Matthey, Kolkata, India. K₂PtCl₆ was prepared followed by reported method⁶. 1-Alkyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole (MeaaiR') and dichloro-{1-alkyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole}platinum(II), Pt(MeaaiR')Cl₂, were prepared according to the published procedure⁷. Pyridine (Py, Merck), 4-methyl-pyridine (4-MePy, Lancaster, U.K.), 4-(*N,N*-dimethyl)pyridine (4-NMe₂Py, Lancaster, U.K.) were of reagent grade and used without further purification. Dichloromethane, acetonitrile, alcohols were purified before use⁸. Nitrogen gas was puri-

fied by bubbling through alkaline pyrogallol solution and concentrated H₂SO₄. Silica gel (60-120 mesh) for column chromatography was obtained from Sisco Research Lab, Mumbai, India. Instrumentation is described earlier⁷.

*Preparation of bis-(pyridine){1-methyl-2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole}platinum(II) perchlorate, monohydrate [Pt(MeaaiMe)(Py)₂](ClO₄)₂.H₂O (2a) :*

To a suspension of Pt(MeaaiMe)Cl₂ (0.3 g, 0.64 mmol) in CH₃CN (30 cm³) AgNO₃ (aq.) (0.28 g, 1.65 mmol) was added and was refluxed for 0.5 h in a carbon paper covered arrangement (to avoid any photochemical reduction to metallic Ag). The precipitated AgCl was filtered off through a G-4 crucible. To this filtrate pyridine (Py; 0.13 g, 1.65 mmol) in CH₃CN (5 cm³) was added in dropwise then refluxed for further 2 h. The solution was then evaporated by bubbling N₂ gas to half of its original volume. A saturated solution of NaClO₄(aq.) (4 cm³) was added into it and the solution was kept in freeze at 5°C overnight. The precipitated dark mass was filtered, washed with water, ice cold EtOH and dried. The product, dissolved in minimum volume of CH₂Cl₂, was chromatographed over a silica gel column. A red band was eluted by C₇H₈-CH₃CN (1 : 1, v/v) and evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. Yield : 0.38 g (76%).

All other complexes were prepared by the above procedure and isolated, yield were in the range 65-80%.

Results and discussion

The complexes are prepared by following eq. (1) in Scheme 1. Ag⁺ acts as chlorine scavenger and increases rate

of the substitution reaction. The analytically pure complexes are isolated by chromatographic purification process in a moderate yield (>60%). The direct reaction between

Scheme 1

$\text{Pt}(\text{MeaaiMe})\text{Cl}_2$ and pyridine under refluxing condition for more than 12 h in acetonitrile also isolated the same product. $[\text{Pt}(\text{MeaaiMe})(\text{Py})_2]^{2+}$ in a poor yield (<15%). The complexes are soluble in common organic solvents (CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2 , CH_3CN , MeOH, EtOH) but insoluble in n-hexane, toluene. The composition of the complexes is supported by elemental analyses (C, H, N). They exhibit 1 : 2 electrolytic nature (Λ_M : 220–260 $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$) in CH_3CN solution (Table 1).

The absence of $\nu(\text{Pt}-\text{Cl})$ at 325–320 and 295–290 cm^{-1} are supporting the substitution of the Pt–Cl bonds⁸. The $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$ appears at 1420–1430 cm^{-1} and lies at higher energy than that of precursor complexes, $\text{Pt}(\text{MeaaiR}')\text{Cl}_2$. The strong stretch at 1120–1110, 1100–1085 cm^{-1} along with a weak band at 620–630 cm^{-1} are corresponding to $\nu(\text{ClO}_4)$. A broad, moderately strong band is observed at 3460–3430 cm^{-1} which has been disappeared on heating at around 120°C. This suggests that the stretch is due to $\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ present in the complex.

The solution spectral studies of the complexes in the wavelength range 200–700 nm (Table 1) reveal that a high intense ($\epsilon \sim 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) absorption is observed at 380–395 nm. Two weak bands ($\epsilon \sim 10^3$) appear at 415–430 and

490–520 nm. On comparing with free ligand spectra⁹ we may conclude that the high intense absorption is due to intraligand charge transfer transitions and longer wavelength transition may be due to $d(\text{Pt}) \rightarrow \pi^*$ (ligand/R-Py) transitions⁹.

The ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes are compared with parent, $\text{Pt}(\text{MeaaiR}')\text{Cl}_2$ complexes⁸ and R-Py¹⁰. The significant observation is the appearance of a doublet at the most downfield position which is susceptible to the substituent R in the pyridine ring. Thus, it is assigned to *ortho*-H to pyridine-N (a,a'-H). Other H's (b,b' and c-H) appear at the upperfield side. The 1-R' (R' = CH_3 , CH_2CH_3 , $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), Ar-Me and methyl group in R-Py (4-MePy and 4-NMe₂Py) are particularly useful to establish the coordination of MeaaiR' and R-Py to Pt^{II} . N(1)-Me shows singlet resonance (4.25 ppm); N(1)- $\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_3)$ gives a quartet (~4.4 ppm, J 12.0 Hz) and a triplet (1.4 ppm, J 9.0 Hz). The N(1)- $\text{CH}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)$ shows sharp singlet ~5.7 ppm. Imidazole (4- and 5-H) and *p*-tolyl (7-H to 11-H) protons are upfield shifted by 0.2–0.4 ppm on comparing with respective resonances of parent complex, $\text{Pt}(\text{MeaaiR}')\text{Cl}_2$ ⁸. Imidazole 4-H and *ortho* pyridine-H (a,a'-H) exhibit significant coupling with ^{195}Pt and support the coordination to platinum(II)³.

Electrochemical properties of $[\text{Pt}(\text{MeaaiR}')(\text{R-Py})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ were examined by cyclic voltammetry. Redox data are set out in Table 1. The complexes exhibit four reductive responses at negative to Ag/AgCl, reference electrode. Of them two are quasireversible as evident from their peak-to-peak separation ($\Delta E_p > 100 \text{ mV}$). Other two redox responses are irreversible and do not show anodic response on scan reversal. The reductions are due to accommodation of two electrons into LUMO's. Less negative first two reductions (0.01 to -0.1; -0.2 to -0.4 V) may be assigned to the reduction of coordinated azoimine function. This conjecture is based on literature results¹¹ in which some of the reports have been supported by EHMO calculation¹². Azo group in the chelating function can accommodate two electrons showing azo/azo⁻ and azo⁻/azo²⁻ reductions⁷. The coordinated pyridines are also active agent to accept electrons. Because of higher redox efficiency of azo group in conjugation with imine function ($-\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) in a competition with R-Py the lower reduction potentials may be ascribed to the reduction of azo group. On comparing with parent chloro compounds, $\text{Pt}(\text{MeaaiR}')\text{Cl}_2$ it is observed that $[\text{Pt}(\text{MeaaiR}')(\text{RPy})_2]^{2+}$ show reduction potential at less negative values (shifted by 0.4–0.6 V). This is in agreement with the better stabilisation of LUMOs in a

Note

Table 1. Elemental analyses^a, conductance^b, UV-vis spectroscopic^c and cyclic voltammetric^d data of [Pt(MeaaiR')(R-Py)₂].H₂O (2-4)

Compd.	Elemental analyses (%):			Conductance data (Λ _M , Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)	UV-vis spectral data λ _{max} /nm (10 ⁻³ ε. mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Cyclic voltammetric (V)			
	Found (Calcd)					E _{1/2} ¹	E _{1/2} ²	E _{pc} ³	E _{pc} ⁴
	C	H	N						
[Pt(MeaaiMe)(Py) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O (2a)	28.0 (28.1)	3.0 (3.1)	10.8 (10.9)	220	520 (3.58), 424 (12.60), 388 (15.66), 358 (5.54)	-0.020 (100)	-0.29 (140)	-0.62	-0.82
[Pt(MeaaiMe)(4-MePy) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O (2b)	30.0 (30.1)	3.7 (3.8)	10.4 (10.5)	242	520 (1.99), 420 (9.01), 380 (15.27), 360 (6.08)	-0.086 (110)	-0.319 (120)	-0.70	-0.99
[Pt(MeaaiMe)(4-NMe ₂ Py) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O (2c)	30.9 (30.8)	3.9 (4.0)	13.0 (13.1)	238	520 (3.50), 418 (13.81), 382 (11.84), 355 (4.62)	-0.13 (120)	-0.408 (130)	-0.92	-1.28
[Pt(MeaaiCH ₂ CH ₃)(Py) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O (3a)	29.0 (29.1)	3.2 (3.3)	10.6 (10.7)	225	502 (4.48), 420 (9.22), 394 (9.74), 362 (9.95)	-0.008 (120)	-0.214 (140)	-0.88	-1.04
[Pt(MeaaiCH ₂ CH ₃)(4-MePy) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O (3b)	30.9 (31.0)	3.8 (3.9)	10.2 (10.3)	228	520 (2.14), 424 (8.97), 380 (14.95), 360 (10.91)	0.012 (120)	-0.189 (140)	-0.92	-1.11
[Pt(MeaaiCH ₂ CH ₃)(4-NMe ₂ Py) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O (3c)	31.5 (31.7)	4.2 (4.1)	12.7 (12.9)	256	524 (2.66), 422 (4.44), 395 (9.89), 368 (6.85)	-0.022 (120)	-0.161 (150)	-0.803	-1.12
[Pt(MeaaiCH ₂ Ph)(Py) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O (4a)	33.8 (34.0)	3.2 (3.3)	9.8 (9.9)	235	520 (2.98), 424 (9.19), 390 (11.54), 362 (8.31)	0.011 (120)	-0.239 (140)	-0.806	-1.26
[Pt(MeaaiCH ₂ Ph)(4-MePy) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O (4b)	35.5 (35.6)	3.8 (3.9)	9.5 (9.6)	230	524 (3.04), 420 (2.89), 386 (18.64), 378 (18.51)	-0.074 (100)	-0.239 (140)	-0.801	-1.38
[Pt(MeaaiCH ₂ Ph)(4-NMe ₂ Py) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ .H ₂ O (4c)	35.9 (36.0)	4.0 (4.1)	11.9 (12.0)	224	506 (1.72), 415 (6.95), 378 (11.85), 360 (7.44)	-0.095 (100)	-0.254 (140)	-0.804	-1.30

^aCalculated values are in parentheses; ^bin MeCN; ^cUV-vis spectra are recorded in MeCN; ^dsolvent: MeCN, supporting electrolyte, [nBu₄N][ClO₄] (0.1 mol), working electrode: Pt-disk micro-electrode, auxiliary: Pt-wire, reference electrode: Ag/AgCl, potential E_{1/2} = 0.5 (E_{pa} + E_{pc}) in V, peak-to-peak separation ΔE_p (= |E_{pa} - E_{pc}|) in mV, E_{pa} = anodic peak potential, E_{pc} = cathodic peak potential. Ligand reduction potentials are designated as E_{1/2}¹ and E_{1/2}² to coordinated azoimine function of MeaaiR' and E_{pc}³ and E_{pc}⁴ refer to reduction of R-Py.

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectra^a of [Pt(MeaaiR')(R-Py)₂](ClO₄)₂.H₂O (2-4) in CDCl₃

Compd.	δ/ppm (J/Hz)									
	4-H ^{b,h}	5-H ^b	7,11-H ^b	8,10-H ^b	a-a'-H ^b	b,b'-H	c-H	N(1)-R	9-Me ^{d,f}	R ^d
2a	7.14 (6.0)	6.94 (6.0)	7.68 (8.0)	7.40 (8.0)	8.98 (8.0)	8.40 ^c	8.53 ^c	4.25 ^d	2.38	
2b	7.10 (6.0)	6.95 (6.0)	7.65 (8.0)	7.39 (8.0)	8.82 (8.0)	8.32 ^b (8.0)		4.22 ^d	2.36	2.45
2c	7.05 (6.0)	6.82 (6.0)	7.58 (8.0)	7.46 (8.0)	8.06 (8.0)	6.61 ^b (8.0)		4.24 ^d	2.38	3.06
3a	7.18 (6.0)	6.89 (6.0)	7.68 (8.0)	7.43 (8.0)	8.95 (8.0)	8.36 ^c	8.50 ^c	4.44 (12.0) ^e , 1.45 (9.0) ^f	2.35	
3b	7.15 (6.0)	6.99 (6.0)	7.65 (8.0)	7.40 (8.0)	8.77 (8.0)	8.30 ^b (8.0)		4.40 (14.0) ^e , 1.44 (9.0) ^f	2.40	2.54
3c	7.08 (6.0)	6.85 (6.0)	7.60 (8.0)	7.40 (8.0)	8.10 (8.0)	6.70 (8.0)		4.40 (12.0) ^e , 1.45 (9.0) ^f	2.35	3.05
4a	7.20 (6.0)	6.94 (6.0)	7.70 (8.0)	7.43 (8.0)	8.95 (8.0)	8.44 (8.0)	8.50	5.81 ^d	2.40	7.30-7.45
4b	7.16 (6.0)	7.00 (6.0)	7.66 (8.0)	7.40 (8.0)	8.80 (8.0)	8.28 (8.0)		5.76 ^d	2.41	7.30-7.45
4c	7.09 (6.0)	6.88 (6.0)	7.66 (8.0)	7.38 (8.0)	8.14 (8.0)	6.90 (8.0)		5.75 ^d	2.40	7.30-7.45

^aCoupling constants are in parentheses; ^bdoublet; ^cmultiplet; ^dsinglet; ^eδ [N(1)CH₂(CH₃)], quartet; ^fδ [N(1)(CH₂)CH₃], triplet; ^gδ (phenyl protons of [N(1)-CH₂]-C₆H₅ group; ^h³J(¹⁹⁵Pt-H) = 25-30 Hz.

PtN₄ environment (N are sp²-hybridised) with respect to PtN₂Cl₂ coordination sphere. This is because of higher π-acidity of N(sp²) donor center than Cl⁻ group. Last two reductions at more negative values are assigned to the reductions of coordinated R-Py group and the reduced species is unstable.

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